

IMPORTANCY OF LISTENING ACTIVITIES FOR LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract: This article provides information about the role of listening tasks for learning foreign language, receiving information through listening music, watching movies and understanding of language can improve listener's skill. Active listening takes important part in practicing language, improves grammar and enhances language proficiency. Listening to other people, speaking enables learner to develop vocabulary, comprehension and language skills.

Key words: listening comprehension, listening strategies, listening skill, active listening, listening elements, practice.

Listening has a positive effect on learning English. Regular exposure to English through listening to music, films, and other media helps increase vocabulary and understanding of the language. Listening is a fundamental language skill that allows learners to receive information and interact with others. It is particularly important for developing speaking skills, as learners who can understand spoken English often struggle to have conversations in English. Additionally, listening plays a crucial role in language acquisition and comprehension, and integrating pronunciation training with listening activities can enhance listening skills.

Listening stands between writing, reading, and speaking as practical skills widely used in daily life. Learning listening will assist us in improving another targeted skill considerably. People demand to hear several types of English repeatedly and continuously if they want to communicate appropriately, meaningfully, and naturally.

Listening provides language input because it refers to receptive skills. By emphasizing the role of comprehensible input, second language acquisition research has given a major boost to listening.

As Rost (1994) points out, listening is vital in the language classroom because *it provides input for the learner*. Listening comprehension is one of the essential skills in the foreign language learning process because a person must fully know what he hears and then provide appropriate feedback for it. Listening

is the most critical skill which is endlessly used in everyday life. When listening, we are reviewing a lot of English usage such as vocabulary, grammatical structures, intonation, accent and our own interpretation. *We can learn new words and expressions by hearing them frequently.* When we actively listen, we engage with the speaker, focus on their words, and make an effort to understand their message. This level of *attentiveness allows us to absorb new vocabulary, improve grammar and sentence structure, and enhance our overall language proficiency. Listening skills are essential for students' academic success in school. They contribute to effective learning, classroom engagement, and academic performance. By actively listening, students can comprehend and retain information, actively participate in class discussions, and achieve higher grades. Listening to other people speaking enables children to develop vocabulary, comprehension and language skills.* These important communication skills are the building bricks of literacy and learning. Active listening activities *promote mindful thinking. They encourage thoughtful, attentive communication and connect students to the speaker through both verbal and non-verbal cues. But it's a skill that needs to be practiced and honed, especially for younger students.*

When learning a new language, the fastest and most effective way to absorb new material is by actively listening. You'll be able to engage with what you're hearing on a deeper level, even if you don't understand what's being said. First, effective listening can help you become a better student. Second, effective listening can help you become more effective in your interpersonal relationships. Third, effective listening can lead others to perceive you as more intelligent. Lastly, effective listening can help you become a stronger public speaker. Equally important, testing conditions that influenced listening comprehension covered time limits, multiple hearings, and note-taking.

Students encountered some problems in listening, such as recognizing vocabulary, rapid speech rate, and linking sounds between words (Chen, 2013). Renukadevi (2014) argued about listening strategy, that listening strategies are approaches or activities that help people remember what they have heard.

In recent years, various listening strategies have been developed to match a variety of listening situations. As a result, language learners are aided in adapting their listening behavior to deal with various situations, types of input, and listening purposes when learning listening skills.

Listening strategies based on the input processes of the learner. The first is the top-down strategy (listener-based), and the second is the bottom-up strategy (text-based). Both language learners and teachers might prefer some

strategies to others. It increases concerns about identifying the most efficient and less efficient listening strategies to teach listening skills. These strategies need to be taught to enable the language learners to deal with their speech, mainly when comprehension is incomplete.

According to Rost (2002), listening appreciation is a complex communicative process in which audiences participate in the active production of meaning.

There are two elements of listening: macro and micro-skills cannot be separated. Macro skills are easier to comprehend since it simply means comprehending what is being said. However, micro-skills are a little more complicated to understand. It is not only about understanding as a whole, but we should consider things like choice of vocabulary, intonation, attitude, deeper meanings, and a lot more.

Moreover, Brown (2004) argues that micro-skills involve understanding what someone says to us. The listener should retain chunks of language in short-term memory and distinguish among the distinctive sounds in the new language. Furthermore, it recognizes stress and rhythm patterns, tone patterns, and intonational contours. It recognizes reduced forms of words, discriminates word boundaries, recognizes typical word-order patterns, and recognizes vocabulary. Listening and speaking are involved as a packet of spoken language. Learners must be helped with any practical listening course (Richard & Renandya, 2010). Quality material for a listening task should further guide the learners to communicate effectively in the target language.

Hammond (2013) discovered some difficulties in learning listening skills. The result is about the comprehension issues learners face, such as rapid pronunciation speed, insufficient vocabulary, speakers' accents, lack of concentration, anxiety, and impaired recording quality. Students' anxiety, lack of vocabulary, and poor concentration were significant the listening problems regarding by EFL students. Meanwhile, several extern aspects like speed delivery of speaking (fluency), pronunciation, accent, and low recording quality can also make students challenging to understand the spoken text. We know that English has many accents and different ways of pronunciation: American, Australian, and British. It brings challenges for both EFL and even ESL learners.

According to Nation (2009), there are two kinds of listening:

1. One-way listening is typically associated with the transfer of information (transactional listening).
2. Two-way listening is typically associated with maintaining social relations (interactional listening).

Traditionally, listening was associated with the transmission of information, and it is the one-way of listening. We can see this in the extensive use of monologues in older listening materials. To help students overcome their difficulties with listening comprehension, teachers must develop effective listening strategies for them. According to Hamouda (2013), teachers can at least give students with appropriate listening materials, background, and language knowledge, enabling skills, pleasant classroom environments, and practical exercises.

Tarigan in Mandarani (2016) argues, that the implementation of bottom-up and top-down strategies in listening are some advantages of this strategy. The strategy can help students who have difficulties in listening by building knowledge in the context presented from the audio listening and facilitating students to understand the meaning conveyed from what they have heard. As for the disadvantages of both these strategies, students will find it difficult if they cannot understand the context of what they have heard, such as identifying vocabulary, grammar, and the meaning of a word. Especially in the English language context, both processes contribute to operating the process of listening. Without understanding input appropriately in the listening process, learning cannot get any improvement. In addition, without listening skills, no communication can be reached.

Renukadevi (2014) argues that regarding language skills comprehension when we

communicate, we receive 45% of language competence from listening, 30% from speaking, 15% from reading, and 10% from writing. Listening has to be considered a language learner with the highest percentage of involvement in exchanging information and ineffective communication. Listening, unlike the other language skills, it is felt comparatively have many challenges by the learners. There are many sub-skills included in listening. They are receiving, understanding, remembering, evaluating, and responding. Nevertheless, with the arrival of the English language, teaching has to be crucial, and proficiency and listening

become a thing that must be highlighted. On the other hand, listening is not entirely integrated that can be operated or integrated into the curriculum and required much attention in that setting.

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